

The Tree That Hides the Forest? Testing the Construct Validity of ViCLAS through an Empirical Study of Missing Data

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Introduction

The identification of serial offenders has been one of the major topics of concern for criminal investigators throughout time. Both the anthropometric classification of offenders by Bertillon in the late 19th century (Bertillon, 1885) and the classifications of fingerprints in the early 20th (Champod, Lennard, Margot, & Stoilovic, 2017) can be seen as attempts to establish databases that would help identify serial offenders. These databases were based on objective information that could be collected in a relatively simple way whenever the offenders were known to the police or on the basis of the traces left by them in the crime scene. The Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) databases developed since the 1980s follow the same logic (Ribaux, 2014). Conversely, it is harder to get information on the psychological characteristics of the offenders and to reach objectivity on the evaluation of these characteristics. It is true that the growth of the psychological sciences during the 20th century led to the formalisation of a vast amount of knowledge about the psychology of offenders, but the existence of different schools of psychology, as well as the quite often dissimilar evaluations of the same offender made by different psychologists, show that there is still an important margin of subjectivity in this kind of information. In spite of that, police databases currently include variables inspired by what is traditionally known as the behavioural approach but is currently labelled as psychological profiling, a technique that attempts to identify the main characteristics of the personality of a suspect on the basis of the elements of his or her crime (Beauregard & Proulx, 2001). Often, however, these elements are not sufficient to dress a psychological profile of the offender. As a consequence, even if this kind of data is particularly relevant for police investigation, there is a risk of developing databases in which a lot of the information required is left blank.

The data left blank in a database are known as the missing data. In that perspective, a typical database corresponds to a rectangular data matrix in which the rows represent units and the columns represent the variables measured for each unit (Little & Rubin, 2014). In the case of a criminal database, the units are usually suspects or criminal events, and the variables correspond to the characteristics of them, such as the place where each event took place, the gender of each suspect, or specific signs of psychopathology revealed by his or her behaviour. When studying the data not reported for the variables included in a database, researchers pay special attention to their distribution, which can be random or not (Little & Rubin, 2014). When few data are missing for a variable, the reasons for that lack of data are usually found at the individual level—for example, in a survey, a few respondents may not know the answer to a question, may not understand the question or may simply refuse to respond (Schafer & Graham, 2002)—and therefore the missing data can be considered as randomly distributed. On the contrary, if the missing data follow a pattern—for example, if the information required by a variable is frequently or systematically absent—they are considered as non-randomly distributed, and there is reason to start seeking for general causes at the level of the construction of the database. In the example of the survey, if the majority of the respondents do not answer a question, one should check whether that question is formulated in a wrong

way, or refers to information that is considered by the respondents as too sensitive, or simply irrelevant.

While random missing data can be considered as inevitable, non-random missing data raise questions about the relevance of the variables included in the database. In the case of a criminal database with information about the characteristics of criminal events, missing data could mean that the crime analyst filling the database does not have the information required or, if the analyst has enough freedom to decide what to include in it, that he or she considers the information useless or simply does not have the time to introduce it in the database. In that perspective, it is important to identify whether the missing data are distributed randomly or not, because a non-random distribution suggests that the database would benefit of a modification. For example, if the goal is to use the information included in the variables of the database to create links between different events, the variables for which most of the data are missing do not allow the creation of such links, and therefore are not suitable to reach that goal.

In that perspective, this paper aims to measure the level and patterns of missing data in a database developed for the study of serial sexual and violent offences, and to identify their possible causes. The database analysed is the Violent Crime Linkage Analysis System, better known by its acronym ViCLAS. On the basis of our review of the literature, we hypothesise that (a) the level of missing data is high, that (b) the pattern of the missing data is not random, and that (c) the pattern of the missing data is influenced by the type of characteristics required by the variables included in the database. In that context, our analysis follows two axes: Objectivity-Subjectivity and Simplicity-Complexity. We estimate that the quantity of missing data will be higher for variables that are subjective and complex —like the behavioural characteristics of the offender— than for those who are objective and simple, like the variables inspired by the situational approach in criminology (Cohen & Felson, 1979; Cornish & Clarke, 2014/1986).

In the first part of the paper we present the origins and scope of ViCLAS, and we summarise the main discussions about its validity and reliability. Then we present the data and methods used for this study, which is based on the French ViCLAS database. This is followed by the presentation of our findings and a discussion of them. In the conclusion, we raise the question of whether the database should give priority to the variables that are objective and simple to collect, we suggest the possible policy implications of such an approach, and we mention the main limitation of our study.

The origins and scope of ViCLAS

In the early 1990s, the Royal Canadian Mounted Police (RCMP) developed the Violent Crime Linkage Analysis System (Martineau & Corey, 2008). Since its inception, the tool targets specific serial crimes that have a sexual and/or violent component. Its specific goal is to help the classic investigation of these crimes by collecting information on each of them with the

aim of facilitating the task of establishing links between the ones that are connected. The use of this tool is particularly recommended for a series of crimes, solved or unsolved, committed without apparent motive, and presenting a serial and/or sexual component (Collins, Johnson, Choy, Davidson, & MacKay, 1998). These include completed and attempted *homicides*, *rapes*, *sexual assaults* and non-parental *abductions*, as well as *unexplained disappearances* with a supposed criminal intervention.

ViCLAS was inspired by previous existing similar tools, namely the *Violent Crime Apprehension Program* (ViCAP) created by the Federal Bureau of Investigation of the United States of America (USA), the *Iowa State Sex Crimes Analysis System*, the *Minnesota State Sex Crimes Analysis Program* (MINN/SCAP), the *Washington State Homicide Investigation Tracking System* (HITS), and the *New York State Homicide Investigation and Lead* (HALT) (Collins et al., 1998). Its first version was based on a questionnaire that included 263 items for each crime.

In practice, ViCLAS acts mainly as a database that collects information on the characteristics of the crime, the victim(s) and the offender(s). The logic reasoning is that by collecting all this information it would be possible to link cases with a similar profile. However, the database does not provide an algorithm that could help link cases. Such links have to be made by the crime analysts who have access to the database. Logically, this task becomes more difficult as the number of cases included in the database increases. Furthermore, the presence of missing data makes this task even more complicated and its consequences are twofold. First, if the data are not present, it is impossible to establish links between events that should be connected. Second, if the data are available for one crime but not for another that is indeed connected to the first one, the analyst could conclude that the characteristic is not present in the second crime and fail to make the link.

The validity and reliability of ViCLAS

The analysis of the scientific validity and reliability of ViCLAS is made difficult because of the secrecy that is kept about its content. According to its creators: “Even the disclosure of a blank booklet [which contains the questionnaire] is cause for concern as we do not want to educate the criminal element as to the types of behaviour that we find particularly important. Disclosure of certain portions of the booklet would be injurious to this sensitive and extremely important investigative technique” (Royal Canadian Mounted Police, 2017). As a consequence, during roughly 15 years, there were no scientific evaluations of ViCLAS (Margot, 2009). Since then, few evaluations have been conducted (Snook, Luther, & MacDonald, 2015) and they tend to focus on its reliability —defined as its capacity to produce intersubjective and replicable measures— and its construct validity, defined as the appropriateness of the theoretical approaches on which the questionnaire is based and their operationalisation (Aebi, 2006). No evaluation of its empirical validity has been conducted because such evaluation would require the comparison of ViCLAS with another similar tool.

Concerning the reliability of ViCLAS, one of the available studies can be qualified as an auto-evaluation since it was performed by the RCMP (Martineau & Corey, 2008), and the other was conducted by a group of academics (Bennell, Snook, MacDonald, House, & Taylor, 2012). Both have a similar research design, which consists in submitting identical cases to several criminal investigators who are asked to code them in ViCLAS, and analysing afterwards the convergences and divergences in their codifications (Snook, Luther, House, Bennell, & Taylor, 2012). Such analysis allows producing reliability scores, which are high when there is convergence (i.e. when the codifications of different investigators are similar) and low when there are divergences. The auto-evaluation study of Martineau and Corey (2008) achieves a reliability score of 87.7% for the percent agreement measure and 25.4% for the occurrence percent agreement measure. Snook et al. (2012) consider that only the occurrence percent agreement measure is a valid measure of the reliability of ViCLAS and find for it a score of 30.8%. These low scores reveal the two weak points of the tools. The first one is its administrative complexity —provoked by the large number of variables and answer modalities included— and has been criticised by other authors (Bennell et al., 2012; Marin, Poirret, Quemener, & Gallois, 2003). The creators of ViCLAS seem to have been aware of that problem because, since its creation, the tool suffered several modifications. Hence, its version 4.0 — which is the one whose reliability was tested by the two studies and is analysed in this research— has already been reduced to 156 items that imply 1140 potential answers. In the rest of this paper, we will refer to the items of the questionnaire as *variables* and to its possible answers as *answer modalities*.

The second weak point identified by Bennell et al. (2012) is related to the difficulties for the criminal investigators to complete the questionnaire without full knowledge of the information required to answer the behavioural variables related to each crime, which are not always available. Some of the data required is hard to obtain from an operational perspective, or require time and specific resources. Moreover, it is sometimes difficult to understand the subtle distinctions between different answer modalities.

This second problem is related to the construct validity of ViCLAS, whose questionnaire is the result of the operationalisation of different theoretical approaches. Basically, ViCLAS is inspired by psychological theories, including the behavioural approach, but it also includes variables related to situational aspects of each crime which stem from the situational approach, as well as descriptive information on victims, offenders and offences (Collins et al., 1998). From a theoretical point of view, this combination is supposed to increase the quantity and quality of the information collected, which in turn should help to analyse, link, and solve cases. From a practical point of view, the multiplication of the information collected and their different nature can have the opposite effect and limit the capacity of the analyst to link cases (Chopin, 2017).

Concerning the use of the behavioural approach, several authors have highlighted its limited empirical support in the field of crime analysis, pointing out in particular that there are no solid studies about the way in which criminal profiling could help manage the links between

different cases (Bourque, Leblanc, Utzschneider, & Wright, 2009; Margot, 2009; Ribaux, 2014; Snook, Cullen, Bennell, Taylor, & Gendreau, 2008). On the contrary, there is relative consensus about the potential of the situational approach to reach that goal. This paradigm, inspired mainly by theories such as routine activities (Cohen & Felson, 1979) and rational choice (Cornish & Clarke, 2014/1986), explains the criminal event by the interaction between the actors (victims and offenders) and the environment of the crime, and has a strong empirical basis and a solid explanatory power, particularly for serial crimes (Beauregard, 2005; Beauregard, Lussier, & Proulx, 2005; Birrer, 2010; Bourque et al., 2009; Ceccato, 2014; Murray, 2007; Ribaux, 2014; Smallbone & Cale, 2016; Snook et al., 2008; Wortley & Mazerolle, 2008). Furthermore, this theoretical approach is particularly adapted for the exploration of police databases (Ribaux, 2014) and has also the advantage of facilitating the identification of criminal patterns (Boba, 2009).

Consequently, in our analysis of the variables included in ViCLAS, we will classify such variables in several clusters, of which two correspond to the behavioural and the situational approach. This will allow us to analyse the distribution of the missing data according to the theories that give scientific support to the tool. In this way, we will be testing the construct validity of ViCLAS which, to the best of our knowledge, has not been tested yet.

Data and methods

The French ViCLAS database

This paper is based on the French ViCLAS database, which is characterised by the fact that the input of the data is centralised. A single unit, based in Paris, receives the ViCLAS questionnaire filled by the field police officers as well as their investigative file and, after verification, introduces the information in the database. This procedure is aimed to enhance the reliability of the tool which, as we have seen, is one of its weak points.

ViCLAS is indeed a relational database that includes two main levels of information. The first level includes several tables with data on the victim(s), the offender(s), the crime, the scene of the crime and the vehicles implied in it. All these tables are interrelated. The second level provides specific details about the data included in the first one. For example, the table on offenders (first level) is linked to a secondary table concerning the use of weapons by them. This table is only used when weapons were used to commit the offence and provides details about such weapons. As a consequence, our analysis is based on the first level of the database, which is the one that should be systematically completed and includes 103 variables.

The database analysed in this paper contains all the information introduced in the database since its creation in 2006 until the end of 2014. That information relates to incidents that took place on the French Territory (metropolitan France and overseas territories) during those years and also before them. Thus, the period effectively covered starts in the mid-1970s. For the years before 2006, the data usually refers to unsolved incidents and to profiles of offenders effectively identified. This procedure allows enhancing the detection power of the

database, which could, for example, put in relation a cold case with a new crime. It must be kept in mind, however, that the information introduced is a subset of all the cases of sexual offences known to the police.

As a consequence, the database (see Table 1) contains a relatively high number of *offenders* (19,006) compared to the number of *victims* (8,090). In a similar perspective, as all the criminal acts that effectively took place during each aggression (e.g. rape, assault and abduction) are effectively recorded, the number of *offences* is also relatively high (14,891). The highest volume of information relates, nevertheless, to the *scene* of the crime (21,487). The reasons are that one aggression can occur in several places and that different places can be recorded for one unsolved case. Finally, the number of *vehicles* identified occupies an intermediate position (8,969).

Strategy of analysis

For the sake of confidentiality, the different variables (N=103) used in our analysis have been regrouped in five different categories according to the kind of characteristics provide by each of them. These categories relate to (a) *sociodemographic* characteristics (e.g. age and sex of victims and offenders), (b) *physical* (e.g. colour of the eyes) *and distinctive* characteristics (e.g. accent), (c) *behavioural* characteristics (e.g. sex practices, anger, negotiation), (d) *situational* characteristics (e.g. lifestyle of victims and offenders, precautions used by offenders, spatiotemporal characteristics of the offence), and (e) *descriptive* characteristics (e.g. description of a car).

For each of the 103 variables we have recoded the available information in three categories: *1* (one) to identify the presence of the answer modality, *0* (zero) to identify its absence, and *missing* when the field had been left blank (no answer). Then, inside each cluster of variables, we have calculated the arithmetic mean and the geometric mean of counting units for which data is (a) reported and (b) missing, as well the standard deviations of both arithmetic means. We also calculated the proportion of reported and missing data for each cluster based on both types of means. In Table 1, however, we summarise the results given priority to the indicators related to the missing data.

The arithmetic mean of the missing values can be heavily affected by a single variable presenting a very high (or low) percentage of missing data, which is technically considered as an *outlier*. For example, in the case of the physical and distinctive characteristics of the offenders, there were two variables for which not a single information had been collected (i.e. the percentage of missing values was 100%). The two zeros in the database were thus replaced by 0.01, which allowed us to calculate the geometric mean. The geometric mean is the average of the n^{th} root of n non-negative numbers, and is used in particular to calculate the average of ratios because it reduces the influence of extreme values (Dodge, 1993, pp. 248-249). Thus, in the case of the offenders, the use of the geometric mean leads to a percentage of missing data of 61% instead of 66% according to the arithmetic mean (see Table 1). Consequently, in our comments we use as a reference the geometric mean.

Findings

Presentation of the findings

The results of our analysis are presented in Table 1, which should be read as follows. The first line indicates that the counting unit for the upper part of the Table is the victim, for which three types of characteristics (sociodemographic, physical/distinctive, and situational) are collected. In the case of the sociodemographic characteristics (line 2 of the Table), the database includes two variables (column 3). The fourth column indicates the total number of victims (8,090). The fifth column provides the arithmetic mean of victims for which data are reported. The figure indicated in the fifth column of the Table (7,925) corresponds thus to the average of the data available for the two sociodemographic variables. In this specific case, there were 7,995 victims for which data were reported for the first variable and 7,856 for which data were reported for the second variable, which leads to an average number of 7,925 victims. Conversely, there were on average 165 victims for which data were missing, as it is indicated in column 6, while the standard deviation of that arithmetic mean corresponds to 98 and is presented in column 7. The 165 missing sociodemographic data represents 2% of the total, as is indicated in column 8 (percentage based on the arithmetic mean). When that percentage is calculated on the basis of the geometric mean of missing data (149, not shown in Table 1), the percentage is also 2% and is presented in column 9 (percentage based on the geometric mean).

In short, data on the two sociodemographic variables included in the database was available, on average, for 7,925 of the 8,090 victims and missing for 165 of them, which implies a percentage of missing data of 2%. The same logic applies to the rest of the Table, with the difference that the counting unit changes from victims to offenders, vehicles, scenes and offences as the reader goes down the Table.

Missing data by counting unit

Figure 1 shows that, for the 20 variables concerning the characteristics of the victim, the percentage of missing data is, on average and according to the geometric mean, 24%. However, the missing data is not distributed evenly because, while for sociodemographic and situational characteristics the percentages are respectively 2% and 13%, for physical/distinctive characteristics they reach 41%.

Regarding the 33 variables describing the characteristics of the offenders, the percentages of missing data are systematically higher than for victims. In particular, the overall average is 47% of missing data, with the highest percentage of them concerning behavioural characteristics (58%), followed by physical/distinctive (61%), situational (28%) and sociodemographic characteristics (11%).

For the 28 variables describing the offence, the average percentage of missing data is 34%, with the highest percentage affecting once more the behavioural characteristics (42%). These are followed by the descriptive (34%) and the situational characteristics (18%) of the offence.

In the case of the scene of the crime, the 7 variables concern situational characteristics and the percentage of missing data is 27%. Finally, in the case of the vehicle, the 15 variables are descriptive and the percentage of missing data is 37%.

Overall view of the available data

If we make a reverse reading of Table 1 by putting the accent on the available instead of on the missing data, the Table can be summarised as follows. In general (i.e. at the level of the counting units), the largest amount of information concerns the variables related to the characteristics of the victim (76% of the data are available), followed by the ones describing the scene of the crime (73%), the offence (66%), the vehicle (63%) and the offender (53%). In particular (i.e. at the level of the type of characteristics), usually the variables for which most of the data are available are the sociodemographic ones, followed by the situational, the descriptive, the physical/distinctive, and the behavioural characteristics.

Discussion

Our analysis shows that the missing data in ViCLAS are not distributed randomly. In that perspective, at the level of the counting units (first column of Table 1), it is somehow not surprising to find few missing data in the variables related to the characteristics of the victims because, in most cases, the offence is reported to the police by them. Something similar happens with the variables regarding the scene of the crime as, in most cases, the place where the offence took place is known and its characteristics can be described easily. These two kinds of variables are indeed objective and simple to collect, and therefore their level of missing data is low, as we hypothesised in the introduction.

The presence of a vehicle when an offence is committed is not the rule—in practice this scenario concerns only 37% of all offences¹— but, whenever that happens, data are missing in only one third of the cases. Lastly, as far as the characteristics of the offenders and the offences are concerned, the relatively high percentage of missing data is mainly due to the presence of behavioural variables, for which data are often rare.

In that perspective, if we concentrate the discussion on the type of characteristics required by the variables (second column of Table 1), it can be seen that 58% of the data on the behavioural characteristics of the offenders are missing, and the percentage is 42% for the ones of the offence. The important difference between the percentages based on the geometric mean and the arithmetic mean—for the latter the percentages are 67% and 55% respectively— corroborates the presence of outliers. In particular, there were four

¹ The 8,969 vehicles included in the database were related to 5,471 out of the 14,891 offences, which implies that quite often there was more than one car involved in each offence.

behavioural variables concerning offences and one concerning offenders for which the percentage of missing data was 95% or higher. Indeed, it is very difficult for the police, and also for the victim, to identify specific aspects of the personality of the author or to put them in relation to his attitude during the offence. Furthermore, it is particularly difficult to remain impartial when qualifying emotions. Collecting data on behavioural characteristics is a complex and subjective task and, as a consequence, the level of missing data is high, as we hypothesised in the introduction.

The second group for which data are rare concerns the physical/distinctive characteristics, which are missing for 61% of the authors (the highest rate of the database) and 41% of the victims. In that context, while some of the physical characteristics of the authors could be remembered by the victim or estimated by the police, it is far more difficult to identify the ones that contribute to make the offender unique, unless they are plainly visible, like in the case of a scar.

The amount of missing information decreases when it comes to the descriptive variables probably because the kind of information required is again relatively objective and simple to collect. Thus, a vehicle or an offence can be described in a relatively impartial way and, consequently, these variables present relatively low levels of missing data (37% and 34% respectively).

In the case of the situational variables, the percentages of missing data are among the lowest, ranging from 13% to 28%. In this case, the information required combines both the qualities of objectivity and simplicity. Indeed, the situational variables are only surpassed by the sociodemographic ones which, as we have mentioned, are the simplest to collect. Thus, data on the sociodemographic characteristics of the victims is almost systematically available (the percentage of missing data is only 2%), and something similar happens with the sociodemographic characteristics of the offenders (missing for 11% of them). This is explained both by the fact that the victim usually has seen the offender and that the database includes profiles of offenders already known to the criminal justice system. The latter correspond, for example, to offenders identified for offences committed before ViCLAS started to be used, but introduced later in the database. In sum, the analysis corroborates the hypothesis that the quantity of missing data is higher for variables that are subjective and complex than for those who are objective and simple.

Conclusion

In this article, we have analysed the level and patterns of missing data in the French ViCLAS database. Our three research hypothesis received empirical support because the analyses show that the percentage of missing data is relatively high and their distribution is not random. In particular, the pattern of the missing data is influenced by the type of characteristics required by each variable.

From a theoretical point of view, one could be tempted to think that, by multiplying the information included in a database like ViCLAS, one also multiplies the possibilities for criminal investigators to solve the cases included in it. However, it is important to keep in mind that the goal of ViCLAS is not to act as an archive database filled with all the available information, but to give support to crime analysts in their task of finding the links between violent serial cases. As it happens in any classification, the aim is to see if, for example, a tree belongs to the same species that populates a forest; however, if one collects too many details about a particular tree, this tree will become unique and it will be difficult to realise that it is indeed related to the forest. Moreover, if such detailed information is required for each tree, but one out of three times it is not available, the task can become close to impossible.

Our empirical analysis of the missing data in the French ViCLAS database suggests that a similar phenomenon is affecting some of the variables included in it. The level of missing data is relatively high (i.e. higher than 40%) for behavioural and physical/distinctive variables and relatively low (i.e. lower than 40%) for sociodemographic, situational and descriptive variables. In terms of the construct validity of the tool, this means that the level of missing data is high for variables inspired by the behavioural approach (a psychological approach) and low for those inspired by the situational approach (a criminological approach). This raises several questions at different levels: Should the ViCLAS questionnaire be reduced to include less variables inspired by the behavioural approach? Should the criminal analysts concentrate their analysis in the variables that have fewer missing values? Would these strategies be effective?

We have no definitive answers to these questions, but we can provide some hints of reflexion. From the perspective of the construction of the questionnaire, it is known, for example, that the ViCAP questionnaire was reduced without losing efficiency (Witzig, 2003). The ViCLAS questionnaire has already been reduced, and it seems a good idea to conduct analyses similar to ours in ViCLAS databases from other countries in order to see if the variables that are usually left blank are the same. If there is a convergence in the results, then the questionnaire could be revised and adapted in order to keep mainly the variables that are objective and simple to collect.

The question of whether such a strategy would be effective is also related to the one of the strategy that should be privileged by crime analysts when establishing links. Indeed, some of the authors that have highlighted the major role played by situational approaches in crime analysis are current or former crime analysts who have used or are using this approach successfully to link cases and establish patterns (Birrer, 2010; Boba, 2009; Ribaux, 2014). In that perspective, the current analysts of ViCLAS could, at least on an experimental basis, try to concentrate their analysis on the situational variables included in it and evaluate the results that they achieve. The available analyses of the reliability of the database (Martineau & Corey, 2008; Snook et al., 2012) could also be replicated, but introducing a distinction similar to ours in the types of variables. This would allow testing whether the codifications of different crime

analysts reach higher levels of convergence for the objective variables and lower levels for the subjective ones.

The question of whether such kind of information could be sufficient to link cases can be studied by analysing the cases already solved and the variables available for them. This kind of analysis will be the subject of a subsequent publication in which we are currently working.

Finally, it must be mentioned that the fact of analysing a database whose content must be kept secret introduces a serious limitation to our study in terms of its general replicability. Indeed, this study could only be replicated by researchers who are also granted access to a ViCLAS database, with whom we could share our classification of the variables. During the writing of this article, we had the constant feeling of walking a thin line between the general information that can be shared publicly and the specific information whose divulgation is forbidden.

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Table 1: Analysis of the missing values in the cases introduced in the French ViCLAS database from 2006 to 2014*

Counting unit	Type of characteristic	Number of variables	N	Average number of counting units for which data is reported (Arithmetic mean)	Missing data				
					Number of counting units		Percentage of counting units		
					Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Based on the arithmetic mean	Based on the geometric mean	
Victim			8090						
	Sociodemographic	2		7925	165	98	2%	2%	
	Physical/distinctive	14		3858	4232	1855	52%	41%	
	Situational	4		6704	1386	1101	17%	13%	
	Sub-total	20		4834	3256	2234	40%	24%	
Offender			19006						
	Sociodemographic	3		16834	2172	951	11%	11%	
	Physical/distinctive	21		6538	12468	4611	66%	61%	
	Behavioural	5		6350	12656	6581	67%	58%	
	Situational	4		13755	5251	229	28%	28%	
	Sub-total	33		8480	10526	5652	55%	47%	
Offence			14891						
	Descriptive	7		8851	6040	4806	41%	34%	
	Behavioural	16		6653	8238	4721	55%	42%	
	Situational	5		11548	3343	2330	22%	18%	
	Sub-total	28		8017	6874	4655	46%	34%	
Scene									
	Situational	7	21487	14364	7123	4855	33%	27%	
Vehicle									
	Descriptive	15	8969	4690	4279	2450	48%	37%	

* Note: The data include cases that took place on the French Territory (metropolitan France and overseas territories) since the mid-1970s.